

DiSSCo Transition Project

**Dissemination and Exploitation (D&E) Plan,
comprising a plan for communication
activities**

Work Package 5 - Deliverable 5.2

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents a detailed overview of the DiSSCo Transition Project's strategy for its dissemination, exploitation, and communication efforts. It covers goals (Section 2), stakeholder groups (Section 4), key messages (Section 5), and specific sections for the project's dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities.

The final part of the deliverable includes an updated overview of the Key Performance Indicators as of M06 and a timeline that places all activities related to the strategy in context.

Keywords

Biodiversity, natural history collections, data infrastructure, digital specimen, artificial intelligence, European Research Infrastructure Consortium

List of abbreviations

CA - Consortium Agreement

D - Deliverable

DiSSCo - Distributed System of Scientific Collections

DTP - DiSSCo Transition Project

GA - Grant Agreement

MS - Milestone

RI - Research Infrastructure

RO - Research Output

WP - Work Package

ERIC – European Research Infrastructure Consortium

DEC – Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan

RIO - Research Ideas and Outcomes journal

DOI - Digital Object Identifier

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1. Introduction

The Distributed System of Scientific Collections (DiSSCo) is a pan-European Research Infrastructure (RI) initiative that aims to bring together natural science collections across Europe in a distributed infrastructure that makes these collections physically and digitally open and accessible for all forms of research and innovation. DiSSCo RI entered the ESFRI roadmap in 2018 and successfully concluded its Preparatory Phase in early 2023. The RI is now transitioning towards the constitution of its legal entity -an ERIC- and the start of its construction programme.

The primary goal of the DiSSCo Transition Project -henceforth DTP- is to ensure the seamless transition of the DiSSCo RI from its Preparatory Phase to the Construction Phase, expected to start in 2025. The transitional character of the project makes it one of its kind in terms of dissemination, exploitation, and communication. Firstly, because many of the mechanisms implemented during its lifespan have already been set up in the project's predecessor, DiSSCo Prepare. DTP will rely on many of these mechanisms, doubling down on some and creating new ones specifically designed for the project's needs. Secondly, because a simple look at the goals of DiSSCo Transition makes it clear that this is a project that will mostly work "behind the curtains". Most of the work that DTP will undertake will involve achieving further development in legal, organisational, data-related, and technological developments, most of which catch the attention mainly of those stakeholders already involved in the future RI. Thirdly, and related to the previous point, because the impact of this transition period will be measured against the increase in the RI's overall Implementation Readiness Level (IRL). DTP will no doubt produce results (see section 8 about the project's KERs) but they are meant to be exploited primarily by the DiSSCo RI community, entrusted with continuing the path of DiSSCo towards becoming an RI.

This deliverable is indebted to the contribution and insights provided by the DTP partners. Several visual examples are provided to illustrate the different measures that the project plans to implement.

2. Main goals

DTP aims to ensure the seamless transition of the DiSSCo RI from its Preparatory Phase to the Construction Phase. For that purpose, the project will address five main goals:

- 1) Advance the DiSSCo ERIC process and complete its policy framework;
- 2) Engage & support DiSSCo National Nodes to strengthen national commitments;
- 3) Advance the development of core e-services to avoid the accumulation of technical debt before the start of the Implementation Phase;
- 4) Continue international collaboration on standards & best practices needed for the DiSSCo service provision; and
- 5) Continue supporting DiSSCo RI interim governance bodies and transition them to the DiSSCo ERIC formal governance.

For the purpose of communicating, disseminating, and exploiting the results of DTP, these general key objectives can be translated into more specific objectives. They are summarised below, indicating the work package that will likely benefit most from achieving them:

DTP main goals	DEC-related objectives	Related WPs
<i>Advance the DiSSCo ERIC process and complete its policy framework</i>	1. Establish a better understanding of how DiSSCo is performing as it progresses to become an ERIC and the potential benefits of this legal form for DiSSCo RI's goals.	WP1
<i>Engage & support DiSSCo National Nodes to strengthen national commitments</i>	1. Contribute to a better understanding among national funders of DiSSCo's contribution to national priorities. 2. Provide accessible materials for Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication to facilitate DiSSCo National Nodes' engagement with their stakeholders at the national level.	WP2
<i>Advance the development of core e-services to avoid the accumulation of technical debt before the start of the Implementation Phase</i>	1. Improve understanding of the advantages of DiSSCo's technical data infrastructure by (potential) users. 2. Provide mainly Dissemination but also Exploitation and Communication-related tools to help DiSSCo Partners share knowledge and create engagement about DiSSCo's technical data infrastructure and end-user services.	WP3 & 4
<i>Continue international collaboration on standards & best practices needed for the DiSSCo service provision</i>	1. Provide Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication-related tools to support DiSSCo's efforts to interoperate and consolidate links with other biodiversity data infrastructures and their respective users.	WP3 & 4

Table 1. DTP-specific goals related to Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation

3. Stakeholder journey

Thanks to the communication and dissemination work of projects like ICEDIG, SYNTHESYS+, Mobilise or DiSSCo Prepare -all of them precursors of DTP- DiSSCo has become a household name for many in the European landscape of RIs and policy-related institutions in the field of biodiversity. Despite that, and beyond specific actions for each

of the stakeholder groups described below, DTP needs to ensure that proper contents and channels are in place both for those who are not familiar with DiSSCo while also serving those who are closer to the project and have a greater degree of knowledge about its features. DTP will aim to provide enough tools to facilitate a logical transition from first contact to interest (lead) and engagement, as well as from engagement to advocacy, as represented in the graph below.:

Fig 1. DTP Stakeholder journey

4. Stakeholder groups

Four main stakeholder groups for DTP have been identified. This section provides a description of these groups and summarises what their main drivers to engage with DTP are, as well as the desired outcomes that are expected from their involvement in the project.

4.1. The DiSSCo community

The DiSSCo community consists of more than 175 collection-holding institutions, including the 16 institutional beneficiaries of the DiSSCo Transition project (DTP) and, very importantly, the institutions that act as national nodes, i.e., the community's national representatives in each of the 23 European countries that participate in DiSSCo RI.

Beyond being the original champions of DiSSCo RI, the community of DiSSCo partners will be, in time, both providers and end-users of the basis of specimen data that DiSSCo RI will make available through its infrastructure and catalogue of services. It is, therefore, crucial to get them knowledgeable of and involved in all the new developments that DTP will bring about. For this purpose, DTP will double down on the mechanisms that were put in place during the Preparatory Phase of DiSSCo -e.g. DiSSCo binnacle, technical blogs, etc.-,

adding new ones to provide its community with timely information on the ongoing progress of the Transition Phase. The Knowledge Area section in dissco.eu or the Roundup of updates (see Section 6.3.1), for example, will be new and important instruments for this.

DTP will also ensure that communication and dissemination activities support DTP's inclusive approach to engaging with the community so that all partners can have their voices heard in important infrastructure and technical matters. In this regard, mechanisms such as opening up the technical sessions in WP3 for members of the community who are not direct beneficiaries of DTP will be instrumental (see 7.3). The goal is that all types and categories of natural history collections within the DiSSCo community are taken into account and have their say.

4.2 Government bodies and agencies

Government bodies and agencies across Europe, especially the 11 current country members of the DiSSCo Funders Forum, are crucial stakeholders of DiSSCo Transition, as they are to provide long-term support for the future DiSSCo RI.

They need to have a clear idea of DiSSCo's value and social impact and how the future RI will address their national priorities. Therefore, it is the duty of the DiSSCo community—and the national nodes in particular—to communicate with them fluidly and constantly.

To facilitate this important work, DiSSCo Transition will ensure that there are various tools for gearing the project's national nodes up and contributing to enable the dialogue at the national level. Dedicated workshops, conferences and tailor-made contents to be used at meetings and disseminated through the project's website and technical platforms are the mechanisms that will take on the task to contribute to DiSSCo's effort of widening its support base and fostering country-level commitment with the future RI.

4.3 European research infrastructures that share DiSSCo's space

There is a growing number of European RIs that share the space of DiSSCo and host the key users of the future DiSSCo RI: bioinformaticians, taxonomists, ecologists, genomics practitioners, etc. DTP needs to reach out to them so that they understand the advantages that DiSSCo RI will bring about. In this regard, dedicated workshops and tailor-made content accessible via the Knowledge Area of dissco.eu will prove as essential tools to facilitate the project's engagement efforts with this group.

Infrastructures in fields close to DiSSCo's, important as they may be to provide a pool of future users of the RI, are more than that. They also host the specialists that, like the ones in DiSSCo, are pushing forward new technical and data solutions that will eventually find their way into natural sciences research: artificial intelligence, machine learning, FAIR data, etc. This is an extremely relevant group that DTP must actively engage and rely on during the development and implementation stages of DiSSCo's data infrastructure and core services. The goal is to make DTP's technical work two-way, promoting the uptake of the

project's technical developments but also consolidating links and ensuring interoperability with the solutions being promoted from other RIs.

Among other activities, DTP's planned scientific workshops about the technical core architecture of DiSSCo (M8) and those devoted to standards interoperability (M12 and M15) will be instrumental, as they will provide the opportunity to share DiSSCo's progress with this important community and gather knowledge and feedback from them. Other mechanisms include DiSSCo's technical platforms (DiSSCo Tech, DiSSCo Labs and DiSSCo's GitHub), the DTP hackathon that is programmed for the end of 2024 (see section 7.5), and the participation of DTP in third-party events, which provide yet another forum to showcase DiSSCo's developments and establish a dialogue with other RIs.

4.4. The wider scientific community

The wider scientific community is represented by research infrastructures and institutions operating in areas such as health, land use, nutrition, climate change, etc. They are also stakeholder groups of DiSSCo, insofar as natural history collections have proved their potential in all these scientific domains.

Vis-à-vis the wider scientific community, not necessarily familiar with the work of DiSSCo, DTP will seek to communicate the need for a new and integrated research infrastructure model like the one that DiSSCo proposes. The Knowledge Area of dissco.eu will be of particular interest, given the scientific yet accessible approach that much of its contents will take.

5. General strategy

If DiSSCo's Preparatory Phase (2018-2023) established the RI's name in the European landscape and paved the way for new organisational and technical development, it is now, during the DiSSCo Transition Phase, when the core work goes to promote and share DiSSCo's *progress*. DTP will surely continue explaining the value and impact of DiSSCo RI, but the project's goals have to do, first and foremost, with tangible progress. For this, DTP will require a refinement of DiSSCo's narratives and methods so that this goal steer all the project's interaction with the different stakeholders.

5.1 Communication

DiSSCo Transition is a necessary part of the development process of DiSSCo RI and, as such, it has relevance and potential to create an impact of its own concerning organisational and technical aspects of DiSSCo RI. That being said, the transitional character of the project makes it almost unavoidable to refer to the future benefits and impact of DiSSCo RI as the finalised product of a long-term endeavour. DTP must,

therefore, find a balance, particularly in its communication activities, between those messages that refer to the individual project and those that deal with DiSSCo RI.

This DEC plan identifies some broad, core messages that will get prominence in the project's communications.

Key messages	Main stakeholders S1: DiSSCo community; S2: Government bodies; S3: Other biodiversity RIs; S4: Scientific community
By advancing the technical and organisational maturity of DiSSCo RI, DTP will directly impact the ability of the distributed community of collection-holding institutions to deliver a European RI.	S1, S3
Technical advancements of DiSSCo's core data infrastructure and e-services will get the European scientific community closer to DiSSCo's "digital twin" vision: a landscape of institutions that exchange open, interlinked digital data, thus ensuring more solid research and reducing the carbon footprint of physical visits to collections.	S1, S2, S3, S4
Through DiSSCo's services such as DiSSCovery (former UCAS), ELViS or the CDD, DiSSCo will set the foundations for a new level of cross-institutional collaboration and connecting AI services to aid this further.	S1, S3
Global challenges require interoperability, standardisation, common procedures and shared understandings of FAIRness of biodiversity-related information at a large scale that starts with the engagement of researchers and institutions as data providers.	S1, S2, S3, S4
A community strongly engaged with DiSSCo's vision will allow the provision of bio and geodiversity data in the format and at the scale needed. This will constitute a reliable and accurate baseline supporting well-informed decision-making in biodiversity-related policies.	S1, S2
The data infrastructure and services will support the Green Deal and Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 by providing AI-assisted mass digitisation to scale up the publication of quality digital data. This will provide a further historical reference for climate change research and monitoring the degradation of global ecosystems.	S1, S2, S3, S4
The adoption of FAIR and open standards, open-source development and the FAIR Digital Object framework have the potential to address the inefficiencies arising from using non-FAIR data.	S1, S3

Table 2. Core messages for DTP communications

Communication takes place alongside the entire lifecycle of the project but it is particularly effective during the first two stages of the Stakeholder journey (see fig. 1). It is at the stage of the first contact and initial interest that the activities for raising awareness and understanding of DiSSCo relevance and impact become crucial, in particular for the group of government-related stakeholders.

Although all the work in communication will be led from WP5, the contribution from all other work packages is paramount, not only to set thematic priorities but also to translate scientific and technical content into more accessible materials for some of DTP's stakeholder groups. That is one of the main challenges of DTP's communications, for which purpose, WP5 has set up a number of bilateral meetings with all work packages so that all communication activities are based on their priorities and implemented with their active participation.

5.2. Dissemination

If communication activities are crucial for those stakeholders in the first stages of the DTP stakeholder journey, dissemination activities will reach out to those stakeholders in the engagement and promotion stages of the journey (e.g. specialised data providers and users). The goal is to contribute to increase engagement and uptake of DiSSCo's technical propositions.

The special character of DTP as a transitional project that builds on previous achievements creates a scenario in which dissemination activities walk hand in hand with communications practically from the beginning of the project. In fact, at the time of submitting this deliverable, some of the dissemination activities of DTP are well under way (e.g. demo sessions of technical developments, specific sections about DTP in disco.eu).

5.3. Exploitation

As mentioned in the introduction, the exploitation strategy of DTP mainly revolves around what comes after the project, namely the construction phase of DiSSCo RI. DTP will create a number of tangible KERs of its own -e.g. technical reports, software developments- but the project's true impact will be ultimately measured against the increment in the overall implementation readiness level of the RI, both in organisational and technical areas. In order to provide a clear picture of this progress, and a solid opportunity to present the project's outputs and possibilities for exploitation, DTP's calendar includes a final wrap-up event (D5.3) a few weeks before the end of the project.

6. Communication activities and channels

6.1 Website

The updated DiSSCo website will showcase a fully branded, specific site for the DTP project with its own sections addressing specific topics of the transitional phase. The website will act as the main access point for all information about DTP along the entire project, including important communication and dissemination tools to serve the different stages of the stakeholder journey, such as the Knowledge Area (see 7.7), the Binnacle (see 6.3) or links to DiSSCo's technical platforms (see 7.6).

Released in its basic form at the outset of the project, the DTP site will continue to be expanded and updated with new sections as the project continues to grow, among them:

- Page devoted to the ERIC roadmap: the work already achieved, the relevance for DTP and future developments.
- Page devoted to Latimer Core, the recently released new data standard for collections in which DiSSCo has had a crucial role.
- Knowledge Area as the repository of all outputs of the project.
- A pathway designed to enable the different target groups to easily access the content that matches their interest and capacities (see fig. 2).

The transitional character of DTP diminishes the possibility of producing developments that could easily be picked up by the media via press releases. Instead, DTP will put the emphasis in generating a high number of web posts that, hosted in dissco.eu and DiSSCo's technical platforms, will be communicated via social media and the project periodicals (see 6.3) and also internally promoted within the community for publication in the digital platforms of DTP's project partners, thus generating visibility for the project.

Fig 2. Customised pathway for DTP Stakeholders (draft)

6.2 Social media

Social media contributes to widening the scope of DTP's outreach efforts, allowing the project to establish its presence within the landscape of biodiversity RIs in Europe and beyond, which is relevant when it comes to issues -such as the concept of the digital twin or the FAIR data principles- that are being debated within the global scientific community.

6.2.1 X (@DiSSCoEU):

X's interactive and fast-paced nature and its popularity within the scientific community, makes it one of DTP's most important social media platforms. The project's activity on X will take the shape of regular posts on specific topics aiming to lead the user to more in-depth information, usually on dissco.eu. DTP also will make the best of X's capabilities as a useful tool for coverage of workshops, conferences and other live events (see 7.1 and 7.3).

Fig 3. DTP profile on X and a recent example of post about the project

6.2.2 LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/dissco/>):

The more corporate/institutional nature of LinkedIn makes this social network an important platform for some specific organisation-related communications. More professional-oriented than X, LinkedIn is also particularly useful for connecting with communities of practice and groups that share the same space as DTP.

6.2.3 YouTube (@disscoresearch):

Since the project's launch, DTP has already been populating DiSSCo's YouTube account with several videos (e.g., DiSSCo's new corporate video, and video demos from the open technical meetings of WP3).

YouTube is widely used to share different forms of videos for all target audiences and DTP is no exception. See sections 6.4 and 7.3 for more information on specific video materials that the project expects to deliver, including more demo sessions, screencast tutorials of different services and short interviews and Q&A videos targeting individual aspects of DTP.

6.3 DiSSCo “periodicals”: DiSSCo Transition Newsletter and the Binnacle

DTP will double down on two periodical mechanisms inherited from DiSSCo’s preparatory phase: DiSSCo’s Newsletter and DiSSCo’s Binnacle (<https://www.dissco.eu/binnacle/>). Both communication tools will play a vital role in fostering cohesiveness and alignment among DiSSCo partners but also, importantly, in introducing first-contact stakeholders to some of the most important aspects of DiSSCo RI in an accessible way. Each of them with their own potential, DTP’s periodicals will reach out to the project’s stakeholders to keep them up to date on the organisational and technical developments that DTP will bring about.

The DTP newsletter will be released four-monthly -unless the project demands otherwise-, featuring the latest updates from the community, such as new technical publications, upcoming events or other relevant issues for DTP partners and its broader community of stakeholders. Distributed via [MailerLite](#), the newsletter builds on the base of subscribers built by DTP’s predecessor, DiSSCo Prepare and has reached 384 subscribers at the time of writing this deliverable.

Fig 4. DTP’s website footer invites users to sign up to the project newsletter

The Binnacle was piloted during DiSSCo Prepare as a means to provide DiSSCo’s community with succinct summaries of some of the major developments taking place in DiSSCo Prepare. The positive reception received from the community has transformed the initiative from a stand-alone platform into a full section in [dissco.eu](https://www.dissco.eu) to explain in simple, visual language all types of topics related to the future DiSSCo RI, both operational (e.g. capacity building) or technical (e.g. DiSSCo’s technical architecture, digitisation workflows).

Fig 5a. A recent iteration of the Binnacle focused on DTP

Each iteration of the Binnacle includes a direct link to a [Padlet](#) page where DiSSCo partners can provide comments and thus have a space for discussion on the topics covered by this initiative, opening up the door for enhanced inclusivity in the internal dialogue of DiSSCo's community.

Fig 5b. Padlet page where users of the Binnacle can leave their feedback

6.3.1 Roundup of updates

It is relevant to reflect on how DTP will address the challenge that the project has a smaller active base than DiSSCo Prepare, which could result in individual colleagues that, overnight, might have less time and/or need to get information via their own involvement in work package tasks or checking the website -a passive tool by design. The monthly

National Nodes meetings (see section 8.1.1) will play a role in keeping them informed but more can be done.

DTP will set up a regular roundup of updates, designed exclusively to ensure that the DiSSCo community remains informed via internal mechanisms. They will consist of a short notification shared via DiSSCo internal channels (e.g., Slack, Teamworks), usually between the distribution of periodicals, that will inform about new developments, referring the user to the source of information.

6.4 Corporate video and other multimedia material for Communications

Videographic materials provide a highly effective and engaging way of presenting information about DTP. In keeping with the multifaceted nature of DTP's stakeholders, a varied group of videos is already being produced for the project so that they serve all stages of the stakeholder journey. Below is a description of the types of videos intended to communicate DTP to the project's non-technical stakeholders. See 7.3 for other, more dissemination-oriented multimedia materials.

Corporate video: DTP will rely on a newly-produced corporate video as the most effective vehicle to communicate the value proposition of the future RI in a way accessible to all stakeholders, in particular government-based ones. Focused on DiSSCo RI's impact in biodiversity research, the video will have a prominent position in all communication activities, both in person and online, and will give way to other shorter video pieces and demonstrators of DiSSCo's data infrastructure and services to support communication and dissemination activities in more specific areas of interest for stakeholders with previous experience in the project's technical developments (see 7.3).

Interviews: DTP will make a trademark of introducing different aspects of the project by means of short interviews with the partners involved. This allows for a personal, engaging way of making DTP understandable to a wide audience. All these "pills" of information ultimately provide a multi-angle, general picture of the project that works as a first stage from where it is possible to go more in detail to other topics.

6.6 Printed materials

DTP is already using a wide range of printed materials to both strengthen the project's brand identity in in-person conferences and events and explain in visual terms a variety of aspects of DTP or DiSSCo RI. See section 9.1 below for more information on the printed materials that DTP is already using for communication and dissemination purposes.

Fig 6. Two posters on different aspects of DTP, produced for the project’s kick-off meeting.

7. Dissemination activities and channels

7.1 National Nodes meetings

As stated above, DTP seeks to guarantee a seamless transition of the DiSSCo RI from its Preparatory Phase to the Construction Phase. This makes the DiSSCo community the main –yet not the only– beneficiary of the project, but also the main agent of it vis-a-vis the government bodies and agencies that are to ensure precisely the next phase of DiSSCo RI. For this reason, it is crucial to keep the community updated on the DiSSCo process and share with them new developments as they are produced, while creating the conditions for a dialogue that allows for feedback whenever needed in core services and other critical dimensions included in the project.

For all this, the (online) monthly recurring meetings, initiated during DiSSCo Prepare, will continue to be the most important forum for dissemination –and ultimately exploitation– with the participating National Nodes of DiSSCo.

7.2 DTP Workshops

The organisation of Technical Workshops and Conferences will act as a major channel for sharing the results of DTP, engaging future users of the DiSSCo RI on the development of the infrastructure and services, and strengthening the links between DiSSCo and the scientific and policy-related communities of stakeholders.

DiSSCo Transition plans to organise four workshops during the project's lifecycle. The ones organised within WP2 (MS2.1 and MS2.2) will ensure that DiSSCo's National Nodes are well-informed about the RI's progress while also allowing DiSSCo to gather feedback on the needs and requirements detected at the national level and from the perspective of other potential users of the RI.

The two workshops of WP4 (MS4.2 and MS4.3) will aim at sharing DiSSCo's technical designs and prototypes with its community. They will also be crucial tools to foster international collaboration around data standards and best practices and to strengthen DiSSCo's links with other European projects and instruments, such as ESFRI.

Topic of the workshop	Project month	Related WP
Virtual workshop on technical core architecture (T2.1 in connection to T3.1)	M8	WP2
Virtual workshop on legal status-quo (T2.1 in connection to T1.2)	M10	WP2
First user and technical stakeholder workshops (Virtual + In-person) on standards in support of the development in WP3 (T4.2)	M12	WP4
Second user and technical stakeholder workshops (Virtual + In-person) on the progress with standards interoperability in the development in WP3 (T4.2)	M15	WP4

Table 3. Summary of the four workshops to be held during DTP lifespan

Each of the workshops will be accompanied by a series of pre-, parallel and post-workshop activities for outreach and dissemination, including:

Pre-workshop	Parallel activities	Post-workshop
Dedicated registration form / page on dissco.eu	Live coverage in social media (X, former Twitter)	Session recordings and presentations available via Youtube and dissco.eu (Knowledge area)
Mailing / social media outreach campaign		Technical publications in DiSSCo and CETAF technical platforms
If applicable, design of specific visuals for the workshop, including an adaptation of DTP's branding		News piece for dissco.eu

Table 4. Pre-, parallel and post-workshop outreach and dissemination activities

Dissemination activities surrounding DiSSCo Transition Project workshops will be a shared responsibility of all the partners, who will provide support and use their resources to provide visibility of these events among their networks.

7.3 Open sessions and video demos

DTP will produce a series of video pieces and demonstrators of DiSSCo's data infrastructure and services to support dissemination activities in more specific areas of interest for stakeholders with previous experience in the project's technical developments. The pieces will include session recordings and pieces specifically produced for the purposes of dissemination (e.g. video-tour of the DiSSCover service).

Video-recordings of demo sessions and workshops: DTP expects to produce a series of specific videos from the open technical sessions from WP3 and from the different workshops that will take place during the project (see 7.2). The goal is to improve the level of engagement and uptake of future users of DiSSCo RI.

Explanatory videos and demonstrators: DTP deals with complex issues. Explanatory videos -usually in the shape of screencast recordings- can highlight, in a non-technical language, the main features of the project's services and developments, something that becomes particularly important for non-scientific audiences.

7.4 Third-party events

Along with generally gaining visibility for the project, attendance at third-party technical events offers DTP the possibility to showcase its technical propositions and make the case for strengthening interoperability among different RIs and initiatives at large, also at the global level. Below is a non-exhaustive list with the third-party events that DTP has included in its calendar for the first months of the project.

Main goals	Types of activity	(specific) Events / workshops	Date
Showcasing technical developments / results from DTP (emphasis on WP3)	Demos, presentations, information for uptake, guidelines for end-users	TDWG MIDS workshop DiSSCo MIDS demo	Feb 22, 2024
		Empowering Biodiversity Research Conference	March 25-26, 2024
		Research Data Alliance 22nd Virtual Plenary Meeting	May 3-4, 2024
		TDWG Latimer Core Workshop - SPNHC-TDWG	Sept 2-6, 2024
		TDWG Latimer Core Presentation - NatSCA	April 19, 2024
Strengthening	Case studies,	FDO as an Interoperability	March 20, 2024

interoperability among RIs (emphasis on WP4)	demos, uptake information, guidelines	Framework for the Biodiversity Digital Twin Project (BioDT)	
		CETAF's Information Science & Technology Commission (ISTC) group meeting	April 29-30, 2024
		International SWAT4HCLS Conference 2024	Feb 26-29, 2024
		International FAIR Digital Objects Implementation Conference	March 19, 2024
		Green Deal Data Space Closing Event	April 23, 2024

Table 5. Preliminary selection of 3rd-party events for the first report period (attendance confirmed)

Similarly to the workshops organised by DTP, attendance to third-party events will entail a number of other complementary activities aiming to provide enhanced visibility to the project, such as making the session recordings and presentations available via Youtube and discco.eu (Knowledge area), producing technical publications for DiSSCo technical platforms when necessary (see 7.6) and producing more accessible web blog posts about the event for the news section of discco.eu.

7.5 Hackathon “Annotate-a-thon!”

Planned for the end of 2024, DTP's virtual hackathon will be connected to one of the project's milestones: *Pilot integration of Machine Learning-assisted services for data enrichment (such as SDR) with DSarch to create a coherent framework enabling seamless integration of machine-annotated data with the Digital Specimens* (MS3.3). The goal is to create machine annotation services (MAS) and test them in the DiSSCo sandbox, the best of which may get into production.

7.6 DiSSCo's technical platforms and Knowledge Base

Similarly to what happened with the DiSSCo periodicals (the Newsletter and Binnacle), DTP will also rely on a number of online technical platforms set up some time ago and inherited from DiSSCo Prepare. The project will indeed further develop and strengthen them with new contents and features:

DiSSCo Tech (<https://discco.tech/>)

DiSSCo Labs (<https://discco.tech/labs/>)

DiSSCo's page in GitHub (<https://github.com/DiSSCo>).

These platforms will document and describe the ongoing technical status of DiSSCo's digital architecture and services, with a special emphasis on the developments that DTP will bring about. They will also constitute essential complements to the project's workshops (see 7.2) and the perfect forum to engage DTP's more technical stakeholders in an ongoing dialogue about the technical development and harmonisation of the future RI.

DTP will reinforce the technical platforms with new articles, training materials, infographics and dedicated videos (see 7.3)

Simultaneously, DiSSCo's Knowledge Base (<https://know.dissco.eu/>)¹ will continue growing to act as the main comprehensive repository for all organisational and technical information about DiSSCo RI, including all developments of DTP and previous stages of the RI.

7.6.1 Technical platforms vs. Knowledge Area vs. Knowledge Base

At this point, clarifying the specific features and purposes of the different repositories that DTP will use for disseminating its outputs seems relevant. As explained above, DTP's technical platforms -DiSSCo Tech, DiSSCo Labs and GitHub- will witness DTP's progress in technical matters. These platforms are meant for those stakeholders already familiar with the data-related aspects of the project. The Knowledge Base is about providing a repository where all DTP outputs are available. That includes much of the content published in DTP's technical platforms but not exclusively and not necessarily in the same format. The Knowledge base aims to serve its contents -technical and not- in a more accessible way and complement them with multimedia content (e.g. Q&A short videos) to help make the materials accessible for those stakeholders with a lesser knowledge of what DiSSCo is developing during its transitional phase.

Finally, the Knowledge Base, is the broadest knowledge repository about DiSSCo. It works as a central search and browse interface to find all documentation related to DiSSCo and DiSSCo-linked projects - DiSSCo Prepare, ICEDIG, MOBILISE, SYNTHESYS+ and more. The contents of the Knowledge Base include training materials, Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs), best practices, guidelines, recommendations, technical documentation and documented decisions.

7.7 DiSSCo Transition's Knowledge Area and thematic pages

The implementation of DTP's Knowledge Area within dissco.eu is yet another pillar of the project's dissemination strategy. Its main goal is to work as a single access point that brings together all the relevant content of the project for the benefit of its stakeholders. Apart from technical content, there will also be other downloadable materials that distinctly state the scientific, technical and socio-economic benefits of the future RI to broad audiences, including policy-related stakeholders and the wider scientific community.

The contents of the Knowledge Area -already being populated at the time of writing this deliverable- will be co-created by DTP's communication team (WP5) in collaboration with

¹ DiSSCo's Knowledge Base has been severely impacted in recent months by a series of cyberattacks against one of DiSSCo's partners, the Museum für Naturkunde, host of the service. At the writing of this deliverable the Base is still not operative. As an alternative, DiSSCo's website provides a link to all deliverables from DiSSCo Prepare, while other documentation (e.g. Data Management Plan, DTP's abridged proposal) are available in Zenodo. We expect that the Knowledge Base will be operative again in the next months.

the other WPs. It will include summaries, multimedia materials, the project's policy brief (D5.4), as well as specific resources to support activities and meetings with government officials and other institutional actors.

Complementary to the dissemination effort through the Knowledge Area are several pages in dissco.eu that will focus on specific aspects of DTP, such as the aforementioned pages on the ERIC roadmap and new collection standards.

7.8 Publications

To boost potential exploitation of the outcomes produced by DTP, the project will publish all relevant papers in the DiSSCo Project Outcomes existing collection at the *Research Ideas and Outcomes* (RIO) journal: https://riojournal.com/topical_collection/207/. For publications deemed of high impact, DTP will encourage its partners to publish their papers in peer-reviewed journals (e.g. European Journal of Taxonomy-EJT).

Reports or software development publications will be assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOIs)#, which will also ease their findability and sharing via other services and platforms (e.g., DataCite, OpenAIRE), providing multiple avenues for exploitation. Additionally, by adhering to open standards and FAIR principles, DiSSCo's output will provide easier access and interoperability to the widest spectrum of stakeholders.

The screenshot shows the RIO journal website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for Home, Articles, About, About Pensoft, Books, Journals, and Blog. A 'Register | Login' link is also present. Below the navigation bar, there is a 'Grant Proposal' badge and a DOI link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.10.e118241> (08 Jan 2024). The article title is 'DiSSCo Transition Abridged Grant Proposal'. Below the title, the authors are listed: Dimitrios Koureas, Laurence Livermore, Wouter Addink, Eva Alonso, Jose M. Alonso, Ana Casino, François Dusoulier, Vânia Ferreira, Jonas Grieb, Quentin Groom, Sharif Islam, Urmas Kõljalg, Gaël Lymer, Karol Marhold, Carole Paleco, Stefaan Pijls, Serge Scory, Ben Scott, Claus Weiland, Katharine Worley. The abstract is partially visible, starting with 'The Distributed System of Scientific Collections (DiSSCo) is a pan-European Research Infrastructure (RI) initiative. DiSSCo aims to bring together natural science collections from 175 museums, botanical gardens, universities and research institutes across 23 countries in a distributed infrastructure that makes these collections physically and digitally open and accessible for all forms of research and innovation. DiSSCo RI entered the ESFRI roadmap in 2018 and successfully concluded its Preparatory Phase in early 2023. The RI is now transitioning towards the constitution of its legal entity (an ERIC) and the start of its scaled-'. On the right side, there is a sidebar with navigation options: Contents, Article Info, Cite, Metrics, Comment, Related, Figs, Tabs, Data, Refs, Cited, Nanopubs, Reviews. There is also a 'Supplementary material 1' section with a DOI link and a brief description: 'Letter of Intent for Collaboration: Development of a Global Partnership on Persistent Identification of Digital Extended Specimens & other Natural Science Collections Data Entities'. The authors are listed as 'Alliance for Biodiversity Knowledge' and the data type is 'PDF'. There is a 'Sign up' button for email alerts and a 'Powered by arpha' logo at the bottom right.

Fig 7. DiSSCo Transition Abridged Grant Proposal published in RIO (<https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.10.e118241>)

7.9 European Commission Dissemination Tools

There are a number of other, free-of-charge dissemination tools set up by the European Commission that will also be of help towards DTP's dissemination efforts. Among them, the ones below have been deemed relevant for the project.

CORDIS. The European Commission's main source of results from the projects funded by the EU's framework programmes for research and innovation. DiSSCo is currently using it as a repository for all its deliverables from the project and DiSSCo-linked projects.

Open Research Europe Platform: An open access, publishing platform for scientific papers for Horizon Europe beneficiaries, including an open peer review and article revision.

Horizon Results Platform: A platform for showcasing research results, finding collaboration opportunities, and exploring the results of other initiatives.

8. Key Exploitable Results

DTP will produce potential Key Exploitable Results (KERs) across its five work packages. All of them, linked to DTP's main goals (see Section 2), are established in the project's Grant Agreement and summarised below:

DTP Key Exploitable Result #1:	Related WP: WP1
Corpus of implementation rules and further regulation for DiSSCo ERIC	
Preparation of the Implementing Rules and Terms of Reference for the DiSSCo ERIC bodies. Preparation of the Financial Rules and the Procurement Rules.	
DTP Key Exploitable Result #2:	Related WP: WP1
Corpus of main policies for DiSSCo ERIC	
Preparation of the policy documents which will be referred to in the Statutes of DiSSCo ERIC, in particular, on the preparation of Access, Data and Employment policies, as well as principles for Intellectual Property Rights (IPR).	
DTP Key Exploitable Result #3:	Related WP: WP2
Participatory schema for DiSSCo National Nodes	
The participatory schema will facilitate shared understanding and vision, consolidate engagement and collaboration, and inform endorsement of DiSSCo requirements and outcomes across the community.	
DTP Key Exploitable Result #4:	Related WP: WP2
Integration and adoption roadmap of assessment tools	
Roadmap supporting the contribution from participating researchers, institutions and nodes in DiSSCo RI with data through well-grounded tools and identified pathways towards ensuring convergence between organisations, and strategic partnerships.	

DTP Key Exploitable Result #5:	Related WP: WP2
Model of training resources for the DiSSCo Helpdesk	
A manual/set of guidelines that will be integrated into the first layer of the DiSSCo Helpdesk, to facilitate understanding, access and exploitation of DiSSCo RI from the users' perspective, ensuring community and capacity building.	
DTP Key Exploitable Result #6:	Related WP: WP3
Minimum Viable Product of Core Infrastructure	
Technology demonstrated in a relevant environment with a representative set of real data, with enough features to attract early-adopter users of DiSSCo RI.	
DTP Key Exploitable Result #7:	Related WP: WP3
Further development of the functionality of ELViS	
ELViS running in an operational environment managed by MNHN, its users migrated and connected to the AAI core infrastructure component and connected with a new service for supporting individual visits.	
DTP Key Exploitable Result #8:	Related WP: WP3
DiSSCo DMP ready for use in the ERIC	
A fully machine-actionable DMP, aligned with European policy objectives and strategies, to enable flexible integration of all relevant information in the data life cycle and the creation of reports containing structured data.	
DTP Key Exploitable Result #9:	Related WP: WP3
Documentation for the enrolment of DiSSCo services into DiSSCo's federated AAI infrastructure services and specify authorization schemas for resources in the infrastructure	
Documentation focused on service enrolment with the AAI services, usage of PID services, documentation for future collaboration in teams on distributed code development, and on documentation for connecting small datasets.	
DTP Key Exploitable Result #10:	Related WP: WP4
Report on state of standards interoperability and gap analysis for next stage of DiSSCo RI development	
Summary of the current state of contemporary data standards that will be required for DiSSCo RI. It will report on the continued testing and evaluation of emerging standards including development of testing plans for pilot integrations with other international infrastructures.	

DTP Key Exploitable Result #11:	Related WP: WP4
Report on standards adoption including workshops, current state of geo-collections data mobilisation and documentation for DiSSCo services	
documentation on DiSSCo’s technical services (APIs) and work with technical stakeholders to implement and support the data standards required by DiSSCo RI. It will summarise community engagement on scientific use cases and implementation from workshops with international collaborators and DiSSCo’s National Nodes.	

DTP Key Exploitable Result #12:	Related WP: WP5
Policy Brief	
The policy brief will ensure that the project’s impact and contribution to EU policy goals and recommendations can inform future policy and programme developments. Information on project results and outcomes will be provided to the EU policy makers, and links with the other Research Infrastructures/and with the EOSC family will be reported.	

8.1 Channels for exploitation and dissemination

8.1.1 National Nodes meetings

The monthly recurring meetings with DiSSCo’s National Nodes representatives were mentioned above as one of the main channels for dissemination. Following a similar logic, they will also be instrumental for making DTP’s results available to the entire DiSSCo consortium, according to their specific needs and priorities.

8.1.2 Wrap-up event (D5.3)

DTP’s strategy for exploitation includes a final in-person Wrap-up Event that will mark the end of the project and, more importantly, provide an excellent opportunity to present its outputs and organise specific in-person sessions to explore the opportunities for exploitation not only for the group of DiSSCo partners, but for its entire community of stakeholders. Presentations, working sessions, demos and specific documentation will be produced as part of the final event.

8.1.3 Other channels

With the only exception of some WP1 deliverables -deemed sensitive from the dissemination point of view- DTP will serve its results following open access principles.

Specific scholarly publications will be produced across DTP’s work packages, including technical papers (WP3 and 4), a dedicated article on the legal processes and methodology for DiSSCo RI (WP1), a paper focused on CETAF’s registry and DiSSCo’s specialisation plan (WP2) and a policy brief from WP5.

Dedicated workshops and attendance to third-party events will also provide an excellent opportunity for specific sessions on exploitation of DTP’s KERs, including training.

Tutorials, video demonstrations and other web-based channels (e.g. Knowledge area in disco.eu, DTP’s periodicals) will also work as dissemination platforms to explain and explore opportunities for exploitation.

9. Activities undertaken to date (M6)

9.1 Branding

Throughout the preparation of the DTP project proposal, a full branding package was designed for extensive use both in internal and external communication channels. The DTP logo is inspired by the original DiSSCo RI logo, already well known within the project’s community of stakeholders. BGE branding is present in every communication material related to the project, from its website and social media to printed materials, video recordings and a series of templates created for DTP partners that include Powerpoint presentations, letterheads, social media designs and deliverables/milestones documents.

Fig 8. DiSSCo Transition branding guide for partners

9.2 Website

DiSSCo’s website will continue to be the main access point for all things DiSSCo, also during DiSSCo Transition. The first months of DTP have witnessed a conscientious effort to start populating the website with new content. The result is a portal with a new visual feeling and, more importantly, a full new DTP specific microsite that is already up and running and provides information about DTP’s goals, programme, outputs and partners.

Fig 9. DiSSCo’s new website, featuring a dedicated microsite for DiSSCo Transition

The DTP dedicated site includes a number of other specific features, mainly the project’s Knowledge Area -under construction at the time of writing this deliverable- but which will eventually host all outputs from the project.

Fig 10. DiSSCo Transition Knowledge Area (in progress)

9.3 Socials

The launching of the DiSSCo Transition project, the production of DiSSCo’s new corporate video and a number of recent, high-impact news related to DiSSCo (e.g. the launching of the German DiSSCo node, the £155 million government grant for DiSSCo UK) has allowed DiSSCo’s socials to welcome the new project with a boost in their numbers, as see in the table below.

DiSSCo Transition socials (Period Jan' 24 - May 24)	
X (formerly Twitter)	
Impressions	13600
Engagement rate	4.85%
Number of new followers	35
LinkedIn	
Impressions	4090
Engagement rate	4.04%
Number of new followers	68

Table 6. DiSSCo Transition social media performance Jan 2023 - May 2024²

9.4 Videos

DiSSCo's new corporate video was released practically at the same time as the launching of DTP. The new piece focuses on those features of DiSSCo -most of them being developed during DTP- that are already outlining, in tangible terms, the impact that the future Research Infrastructure will have in how biodiversity research is done in Europe.

Making extensive use of engaging computer graphics, DiSSCo's new corporate video aims to be the perfect first-contact resource to understand DiSSCo's endeavour. For the same purpose, the piece is structured in a number of sections that can work separately as short-videos with its own message:

- Biodiversity loss and the need to scale up research
- DiSSCo RI model
- The Digital Specimen as the technical cornerstone of DiSSCo
- DiSSCo's new vision of research at scale

² "The engagement rate is a metric used to gauge the level of engagement generated from created content or a brand campaign. It refers to the level of interaction with followers that is generated from content created by a user" (Source: Corporate Finance Institute <https://corporatefinanceinstitute.com/>)

Fig 11. Screenshot of DiSSCo's new corporate video featuring a 3D graph of the digital specimen

DiSSCo's new video has already accumulated more than 800 views in DiSSCo's Youtube channel. Other videos that are already available publicly via DTP's Youtube channel and the project's online platforms include the recordings of the first two demo-sessions from WP3.

9.5 Promotional materials

DTP has already produced a number of printed materials to boost the project's brand identity in in-person events such as workshops or conferences.

DiSSCo 2024 brochure: An up-to-date, summary of DiSSCo's highlights addressed to any potential user that needs to understand DiSSCo's pillars, goals and main outcomes. The 2024 brochure is available for download in the "Resources" section of dissco.eu. It is also available in editable format for DiSSCo partners in the project's drive, so that they can customise it and use it at the national level.

DiSSCo Services catalogue 2024: Similar in format to the brochure, the services catalogue provides a summarised review of DiSSCo's main services that will be developed during DTP. It is also available from the "Resources" section of dissco.eu and in editable format for the project partners.

Fig 12. DiSSCo's services brochure describes in detail each of the services to be developed during DTP

Posters: The first months of DTP have witnessed a complete renovation of some of the visuals that DiSSCo's partners bring to conferences and other events. Such is the case of the two new posters (see Fig.6).

Stickers and other merchandise: DiSSCo Transition is a relatively short project but it will be very active from the perspective of workshops, conferences and other events. For that purpose, the project has developed a brand-new model of stickers that combines images of biodiversity and data-related technology.

Fig 13. DiSSCo Transition partners have already distributed hundreds of stickers in a several events

9.6 DiSSCo periodicals: new issues of DTP's newsletter and the Binnacle

DiSSCo Transition has already released a new issue of the DiSSCo Transition Bulletin -the first to take place during DTP- and the Binnacle. The former generally follows the same format of its predecessor, the DiSSCo Prepare Bulletin, while the latest iteration of the Binnacle is focused on the crucial concept of digitisation: definition, socio-economic benefits, technology, workflows and case studies (follow [this link](#) to access the latest issue of the Binnacle).

Fig 14. The DTP Bulletin follows a well-tested format that includes news, multimedia and important calendar highlights

Fig 15. DiSSCo's last Binnacle is focused on the fundamental concept of digitisation

9.7 Attendance to 3rd party events

Our colleagues from DTP have already attended a good number of the 3rd-party events that were planned for the first months of DTP.

(specific) Events / workshops	Date
TDWG MIDS workshop DiSSCo MIDS demo	Feb 22, 2024
Empowering Biodiversity Research Conference	Mar 25-26, 2024
Research Data Alliance 22nd Virtual Plenary Meeting	May 3-4, 2024
TDWG Latimer Core Presentation - NatSCA	Apr 19, 2024
FDO as an Interoperability Framework for the BioDT Project (BioDT)	Mar 20, 2024
CETAF's Information Science & Technology Commission (ISTC) group meeting	Apr 29-30, 2024
International SWAT4HCLS Conference 2024	Feb 26-29, 2024
International FAIR Digital Objects Implementation Conference	Mar 19, 2024
Green Deal Data Space Closing Event	Apr 23, 2024

Table 7. Third-party events attended by DTP partners as of M06

9.8 Publications

So far, two scholarly publications related to DTP have been published in Research Ideas and Outcomes (RIO):

Islam S, Papale D, Vaira L, Rosati I, Peterseil J, Pichot C (2024) Navigating taxonomic complexity: A use-case report on FAIR scientific name-matching service usage in ENVRI Research Infrastructures. *Research Ideas and Outcomes* 10: e121871. <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.10.e121871>

Koureas D, Livermore L, Addink W, Alonso E, Alonso JM, Casino A, Dusoulier F, Ferreira V, Grieb J, Groom Q, Islam S, Kõljalg U, Lymer G, Marhold K, Paleco C, Pijls S, Scory S, Scott B, Weiland C, Worley K (2024) DiSSCo Transition Abridged Grant Proposal. *Research Ideas and Outcomes* 10: e118241. <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.10.e118241>

10. List of Key Performance Indicators

Area	Item	Output	Target (end of project)
KPIC01	Website	Release of DiSSCo Transition site inside dissco.eu (the existing DiSSCo website)	1 site
		Update of DiSSCo Transition site	1 update
		News items published during the project's lifecycle.	9 publications
KPIC02	DiSSCo Technical platforms	Publications on DiSSCo's (existing) technical platforms: DiSSCoTech, DiSSCo Labs, DiSSCo Github	>6 [combined] publications
KPIC03	DTP featured on 3rd party sites and/or newsletters	Pieces released in relation with DTP	3
KPIC04	Socials	DiSSCo X account, DiSSCo LinkedIn account and DiSSCo Youtube account	~150 extra followers (X), 10% increase in LinkedIn followers (<i>241 followers at the time of this report</i>) >40 subscribers to Youtube account 25000 impression (X), 10000 impressions (LinkedIn) all partners combined
KPIC05	Videos	Corporate video Additional short video pieces (Q&A videos and demonstrators of infrastructure/services)	1 corporate video and minimum 5 short video pieces by the end of the project
KPIC06	Printed materials	General brochure, technical brochure, poster, banner, roll-up, sticker	1 item of each element

KPIC07	Newsletter	DiSSCo Transition Bulletin	>3 issues ~15% increase in number of subscribers (390 at the time of this report)
KPIC08	DiSSCo Binnacle	Publication of in-depth summaries for DiSSCo's Binnacle section on its website	At least 2
KPIC09	Roundup of updates	Internal notifications with updates for the DiSSCo community	At least 3
KPIC10	Communication activities at 3rd party events	Communication activities (i.e. generic presentations of DTP) in events in the field of biodiversity data, including those organised by other Horizon Europe projects	> 2 events >80 attendees combined
KPID01	Knowledge Area (dissco.eu)	Specific section with tailored-made content on the impact of DiSSCo's developments	1
KPID02	Workshops/ webinars	Workshops for WP2 (MS2.1-2.2) and Workshops for WP4 (MS4.2 and MS4.3)	4
		Post-workshop materials (presentations and recordings made widely available)	4
KPID03	Dissemination activities at 3rd party events	Dissemination activities (as per DEC plan) in events in the field of biodiversity and biodiversity data, including those organised by other Horizon Europe projects.	>10 events (combined) >500 attendees (combined)
KPID04	Publications	Publications and papers	At least 2
		Oral and poster abstracts (for conferences or any 3rd party event)	At least 4
KPIE01	Wrap-up event	To present DiSSCo Transition's outputs and its exploitable possibilities	1
KPIE02	Technical outputs	Exploitable technical reports, plans, methodologies and other outputs available via scientific journals and platforms	At least 2
KPIE03	Software developments	Exploitable reports and/or software developments affiliated with DOIs shared via open services and platforms (e.g. DataCite, OpenAIRE)	At least 2
KPIE04	National Nodes engagement	Number of informative and interactive community NN meetings with a quorum of members	>12

Table 8. DiSSCo Transition table of Key Performance Indicators

DISCO R1 TRANSITION						
WPS	Year 2					
	13	14	15	16	17	18
T5.3						
DTP website: updates						
DTP website: highlights						
Social networks: updates and highlights	Coverage Hackathon		Coverage Workshop Wp4	Coverage of DTP Wp4-up event (expected date)		
DTP periodicals: Newsletter	Newsletter #1				Newsletter #3	
DTP periodicals: Binnacle					DTP Binnacle: "Construction Phase of DISSCO"	
Roundup of updates			Roundup of updates			
DTP Workshops	DTP Hackathon (expected date)		2nd user & technical workshop			
Videos	Wp3 technical session (recording to be confirmed)		Wp3 technical session (recording to be confirmed)			
Promotional materials	Q&A Interview 4					
Other comms resources						
Deliverables WPS						

Fig 16. DiSSCo Transition timeline of DEC activities

12. Next steps

DTP will update this DEC plan if necessary and as the project progresses. The normal interaction with the project’s stakeholders and the key developments that the project is expected to achieve will set the pace and direction for the potential update.